

Oral Carcinomas and their Diagnosis and Prevention by Dental Surgeons.

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ABSTRACT:

Objective: Oral carcinomas and the role of dental surgeons in its prompt diagnosis and prevention.

Place of Study: Multiple dental hospitals in Lahore were visited during this study.

Duration of study: This study was completed in a duration of 06 months form July 2018 to January 2019.

Materials and Methods: A carefully designed proforma was formulated which was given to different dental surgeons who were working in various clinics in Lahore and then their answers were used to calculate the role performed by them in early diagnosis and prompt treatment of fatal diseases.

Results: Through examination of the oral mucosa of the patient was examined by 25% of the dentists only. Use of various insultants like tobacco, alcohol and other elements was inquired by almost 70% of the dentists and to avoid these toxins was appreciated by 65% of the doctors. Use of toxic elements predisposing to neoplasia or preventions from them was neglected by around 50% of the doctors. Further exploration for the findings related to oral cancer was done by 9% of the doctors only and biopsy and senior consultation to rule out the oral carcinomas was done by the 6% of the doctors only.

Conclusion: For timely diagnosis and early prevention of oral carcinomas a lot of work has to be done by the dental surgeons as evident by the research. This can only be made possible by the health awareness and promotion by the dental surgeons.

Keywords: Oral Carcinomas, prevention, diagnosis, Dentists

Introduction: Almost 3% of the carcinomas among the world are cancers of the squamous cells, a most common type of oral carcinoma. In under developed countries like India, Pakistan, Brazil and Bangladesh and even in developed countries like France these cancers are much more common. Pan chewing is the leading cause of oral cancer followed by tobacco and alcohol. While in some other countries Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) infection and other elements like chewing of betel

quid and smokeless tobacco are leading factors. Oral cavity is the easily accessible area for examination but identification in almost 50% of the cases is not seen until the signs and symptoms are visible. Poor standards of education, low socio-economic status and life style is leading to an increased incidence of oral cancers. Increased awareness along with early diagnosis and prompt treatment can prevent up to 50% of the oral carcinomas. . Poor standards of education, low socio-economic status, life style, lack of awareness and lack of specialists are leading causes of increased rate of increase oral cancers in Pakistan. Early diagnosis and treatment of oral cancer can be aided by the health care providers but timely diagnosis and prompt treatment must be made by the professional dentists with responsibility. Any suspected lesion in the head, neck or oral region is also included in dental illness.

The main aim of the research was to find the role of dental surgeons in early diagnosis and prevention of oral cancers. Deficiency on the surgeons end have been shown by many researches and is helpful in filling the gaps in treatment. This research will improve the ability of the doctor to look for hidden lesions that may prove fatal later on.

Materials and Methods: Multiple dental hospitals in Lahore were visited during this study. This study was completed in a duration of 06 months form July 2018 to January 2019. A carefully designed proforma was formulated which was given to different dental surgeons who were working in various clinics in Lahore and were willing to take part in the study. Proforma was distributed among 300 different dental surgeons randomly. Examination, history especially use of different addictions like gutca, tobacco and paan was the key feature of the questionnaire along with neoplastic changes in the head and neck area. Clear directions were given to patients to quit these habits. Only those patients were selected who were willing to take part in the research and the confidentiality of

the patient was maintained as a top priority. Questionnaires were collected few days later and only completely filled papers were selected for the study. Calculations were made and the result was formulated.

Results: 300 questionnaires were given to various dental surgeons who were willing to fill the proforma with keen interest. 210 questionnaires were returned timely and were included in the study. Through examination of the oral mucosa of the patient was examined by 25% of the dentists only. Use of various insulants like tobacco, alcohol and other elements was inquired by almost 70% of the dentists and to avoid these toxins was appreciated by 65% of the doctors. Use of toxic elements predisposing to neoplasia or preventions from them was neglected by around 50% of the doctors. Further exploration for the findings related to oral cancer was done by 9% of the doctors only and biopsy and senior consultation to rule out the oral carcinomas was done by the 6% of the doctors only.

Discussion: Smoking is the leading cause of the most frequent cancer in the world i.e. squamous cell carcinoma. Use of different toxins like alcohol, betel nuts, paan or tobacco in any type of form are the main culprits in causing oral cancers and all the health professionals are well aware of this fact. Poor education and awareness campaigns are the key problems that need urgent attention. Proper and correct diagnosis, prevention of the oral cancers and increasing the awareness in dental surgeons was the main feature of this study so that mortality and morbidity associated with oral cancer can be reduced. Important history questions pertaining to history of use of tobacco, alcohol, paan or betel nuts and the data maintenance was done by 35% of the dental surgeons only while stopping the use of toxic elements was advised by 32% of the doctors only. Much needed history about the use of tobacco is not recorded by the dental surgeons as evident by this study which is comparable to other studies. A large number of dentists are not careful about preventing and ending this issue which has caused numerous deaths.

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With proper history, examination of the oral mucosa, head and neck regions and questioning about the use of toxic elements can help in anticipation and diagnosis of the cancerous lesions in a large number of patients. Suspicion of malignant lesion and through examination must be done if a lesion does not heal in a period of 2 weeks with or without treatment or patient may be referred to a senior surgeon. Diagnosis at an early stage can be helpful in treatment which can increase the survival rate. 80% survival rate is seen if the cancer is detected at stage-1 which is reduced to 51% with extent in the nearby regions and decreases to 29.5% with distant regions involvement.

As evident by the current study, surgeries have become the prime target for most of the surgeons leading to negligence of the early diagnosis and prompt treatment of oral cancerous lesions. Increased incidence of the advance malignant lesions resulting in the decreased survival rate is because of this decreased patient care by the health professionals and same has been shown by Shah et al in his study. Key role in diagnosing oral carcinomas at early stages is attributed to dental surgeons and it has been shown in this study that lack of awareness is the main cause in late detection of the oral cancers.

Conclusion: Multiple deaths are recorded every year due to oral cancers which can be avoided easily by timely diagnosis. For timely diagnosis and early prevention of oral carcinomas a lot of work has to be done by the dental surgeons as evident by the research. This can only be made possible by the health awareness and promotion by the dental surgeons. Developing awareness in the patients and their education should be the primary aim of the surgeons. They must participate in the health awareness campaigns and willingly educate the patients about the risk involved in the oral carcinomas to reduce its increasing incidence over the years.

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